

Edible Cities Network – Integrating Edible City Solutions for social, resilient and sustainably productive Cities

Discussion paper

Background and terminology for EdiCitNet WP6 Consultancy, Business Development and Market Uptake

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About the EdiCitNet project

EdiCitNet is demonstrating innovative nature-based solutions (NBS). Edible City Solutions (ECS) are going one step further: We include the whole chain of urban food production, distribution and utilisation for inclusive urban regeneration and address societal challenges such as mass urbanisation, social inequality and climate change and resource protection in cities.

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Glossary

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
EdiCitNet	Edible Cities Network
ECS	Edible City Solutions
UF	Urban Farming
UFG	Urban Food Gardening

Discussion paper: background and terminology for WP6

EDIBLE CITY BUSINESS SOLUTIONS –

WHERE AGRICULTURAL, ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL INNOVATION MEET

1. Executive Summary

We live in exciting times of an unprecedented pace of innovation – and at a point where the earth has entered into a stage popularly known as the Anthropocene age, an age of large-scale planetary destruction. At the same time, humanity has started to develop a human ecology with a perspective of wholeness, or anti-fragmentary view of the world. Never before has there been a more imminent need for innovations that can leapfrog us into zero-emissions, carbon-binding, biodiversity-building, and humanely caring society. EdiCitNet therefore comes at a key point and delivers strong ambitions for taking Edible City Solutions beyond the pilot scale, and finding transition paths to move the most effective innovations in the field onto a worldwide audience. Interestingly, business – if done correctly – can be a significant force for good in making this transition happen.

This document is intended to be a starting point for work package 6 (WP6) of EdiCitNet, by providing some background to the tasks to be undertaken over the duration of the project, and to strive towards a shared understanding of the particular focus of WP6, being on the business/market side of Nature-based Solutions (NBS) and Edible City Solutions (ECS).

2. Introduction

EdiCitNet is not the first EU funded research/innovation to investigate nature-based solutions (NBS) and some of these have also worked specifically on business models in urban agriculture. Former projects include “SustUrbanFoods”, “Allotment Gardens in European Cities”, “Urban Green Education for Enterprising Agricultural Innovation/Urban Green Train”, “Horticulture for Innovative and Inclusive Early Childhood Education” and “Horticulture in towns for Inclusion and Socialisation”. Additionally, there are many higher education institutions across Europe that do significant research on these topics, including the partner universities of this project.

In spite of this, there are significant knowledge gaps, especially in the practical application of the knowledge in communities and especially in business. The ambition of EdiCitNet englobes urban agriculture but also goes beyond purely farming. Edible City Solutions also include closed material and energy flows of a city, using innovative principles of systems thinking and ecological design. These solutions also have a strong relation to social innovation and sustainable entrepreneurship, as more and more people look to combine these ambitions with job creation and elements of green economy. We see, however, that most of the available research looks at this field from the point of view of agriculture and cultivation, and less so from the point of view of the sustainable entrepreneurship or social innovation. We seek to address this knowledge / practice gap throughout WP6, where we will highlight all these aspects of ECS business and explore solutions that go beyond status quo and result in significant impact.

3. Main section

3.1 SETTING THE STAGE, A BRIEF INTRODUCTION

Historically, every city depended on food being produced within the city and along the peri-urban belt for its' sustaining. With the rapid urbanization that most of Europe has undergone over the last couple of centuries, cities have become gradually more dependent on food sourced elsewhere in the country or even globally. In terms of crisis, such as during World War I and II, urban food production has multiplied and been a significant provider of food for the urban consumer also in modern times, but generally speaking, the occupations associated with urban ECS across Europe had almost disappeared by the end of the 20th century.

Presently, we face the challenge to prepare our economy for a reduced consumption of resources and production of emissions while still providing for everybody. This needs at least a partial shift from globalized commodity and service chains to a combination of regionalization and self-sufficiency for many products and services. ECS are an ideal tool for this shift, as they will allow cities and their inhabitants to locally increase their self-sufficiency in many respects and make them resilient to changing conditions on a global scale, including aspects of climate, energy, water, buildings and food of course.

With the new millennia, a new wave of urban ECS has gradually claimed the stage in European cities again. Inhabitants are again learning and implementing ECS skills such as growing vegetables on their balconies, keeping chickens and bees in gardens and establishing community gardens, and small and medium-sized enterprises that provide urban consumers with local and sustainably sourced food. Citizens eager to put their mark on a city or work to provide equitable access to organic food, establish community gardens or vegetable gardens for public consumption in urban spaces such as train station and town squares. These urban consumers range from individuals and families, to restaurants or other types of urban businesses. Prosumer is a term that many use to refer these citizens, that both are producers and consumers of the urban food scene. Many enterprises also combine the food production with programs that positively impact social cohesion, public health and wellness.

It is important for us to emphasize ECS under the EdiCitNet umbrella as a very systemic approach to urban challenges. It is equally important to emphasize that an ECS startup can have direct or indirect impacts on urban ecosystems beyond their core product or service. Indeed, our baseline mapping of cases across Europe demonstrate that it is quite common for these businesses to develop complimentary activities that generate additional ECS and ecosystem- positive and resource smart synergies between such activities.

The EdiCitNet proposal sets forth a very ample definition of what can be included as ECS. These definitions should continue to be quite open-ended throughout the project period, as we believe that many completely new ECS will be invented, piloted, and converted into businesses over the next few years. In short – there is a new awareness of the endless possibilities of the city to be a productive part of a country's food sovereignty and resilience and the EdiCitNet ECS will be trailblazers in that respect.

3.2 SCOPE OF CITY CASES

The diversity in ECS across Europe is immense, and ranges from small family gardens to industrial-size vertical gardens, projects ranging from green ornamental infrastructure such as green walls, and truly edible solutions such as indoors microgreens farming, rooftop beekeeping and indoors mushroom production.

Throughout literature, ECS are often understood as products and services derived from traditional farming activities, taking place in an urban or peri-urban setting. The products and services center around cultivation of flowers, fruits, vegetables and herbs, and to a smaller extent animal husbandry such as keeping backyard chickens.

The last decades have, however, seen a wave of innovation where the scope of food products produced, ecosystem services provided, and the organizational and business models making it happen, have multiplied. Today, people identifying themselves as urban farmers grow mushrooms in containers, keep bees on skyscrapers, brew beer from rainwater gathered on roofs or even cultivate insects to produce protein-rich flour. They produce fish and vegetables in aquaponics, use permaculture approaches in urban agroforestry settings, they store and clean stormwater and some even provide sanitation services to recover the nutrients from excreta. ECS startups are found on rooftops, in basements, on vacant lots, in parks and the premises of schools, hospitals and municipal buildings to mention a few.

As most current literature interprets ECS as urban farming and direct food production, and few look into the other NBS and ecosystem services that EdiCitNet include in our scope of cases, we see already from the onset that not all definitions and available literature englobe the whole range of ECS. However, as the majority of ECS are still found within urban farming, definitions and literature specific to those kinds of cases is still useful.

EdiCitNet interprets ECS in a wide sense and includes many solutions which are mainly recreational or educational, including the possibility to sit and eat fruit from your own garden, establishing insect hotels or relaxing in a rooftop garden. **However, for the scope of WP6 it is useful for us to propose some general thoughts on where to draw the line regarding which initiatives we should include in the tasks and deliverables of this project.**

Key questions to ask ourselves, are therefore;

- Is it a business?
- Is it “just a farm”?
- Is the ECS embedded in the city?
- Is the product or service an ECS?

3.2.1 Is it a Business?

As we have gone through a long list of ECS in Oslo, we have many times had to ask ourselves the basic question of whether an initiative is indeed a business, and thereby whether it belongs as a part of WP6.

It is clear that many ECS do not consider themselves a business, and do not have any activities that could be considered commercial. At the same time the initiatives could be providing important services to the community such as being a place where people with a history of psychiatric illness can feel a sense of belonging as they try to improve their mental health, it can be a very effective arena for language training for refugees, or a great arena for a family to participate in shared activities. However, **not all ECS or NBS are, can be, or are interested in becoming, a business**, and may therefore not be appropriate cases for WP6.

The Merriam-Webster definitions of “business”ⁱ provide a good starting point. Three main dimensions directly related to the scope of this WP would be the following;

- a) A usually commercial or mercantile activity engaged in as a means of livelihood;
- b) A commercial or sometimes industrial enterprise
- c) Dealings or transactions of an economic nature

However, we need to look beyond conventional business when we look into ECS business models, as many of them do not self-define, or fall well into, conventional categories of business. Rather, they may consider themselves social enterprises or similar.

The European Commission published the report “A map of social enterprises and their eco-systems in Europe” in 2015, trying to map the current state of social enterprises across Europe. One of their key outputs was to attempt to refine a shared understanding of what a social enterprise is. Although the definitions vary from country to country, the following were selected as the key elements;

- *An entrepreneurial dimension, i.e. engagement in continuous economic activity, which distinguishes social enterprises from traditional non-profit organisations/ social economy entities (pursuing a social aim and generating some form of self-financing, but not necessarily engaged in regular trading activity);*
- *A social dimension, i.e. a primary and explicit social purpose, which distinguishes social enterprises from mainstream (for-profit) enterprises; and,*
- *A governance dimension, i.e. the existence of mechanisms to ‘lock in’ the social goals of the organisation. The governance dimension, thus, distinguishes social enterprises even more sharply from mainstream enterprises and traditional non-profit organisations/ social economy entities.*

Operationalizing these findings from both the “business” and “social enterprise” world, we are better able to separate ECS activities into business and non-businesses such as NGOs and ensure that the work we will do over the next years in WP6 indeed focuses on “Consultancy, business development and market uptake”.

3.2.2 Is it just “a farm”

Although it might seem contradictory, not all food producers within the municipal borders, should be included in the ECS scope of EdiCitNet. COST-Action Urban Agriculture Europeⁱⁱ defines urban agriculture as “structurally embedded in the urban fabric; it is integrated into the social and cultural life, the economics, and the metabolism of a city”, as opposed to regular agriculture which does not have the same kind of symbiosis with the city and the inhabitants but rather depend on national structures, distribution channel and customers.

Six dimensions of urban agriculture (UA) are identified, being the spatial dimension (where does UA take place?), the functional dimension (what is produced? Is it food or non-food?), the motivational dimension (why does UA take place), the market dimension (where are the products of UA consumed?), the origin dimension (how was the UA initiative started?), and finally the actor dimension (who performs UA).

The sum of these dimensions draws a picture where a conventional farm operating in or near the city, is a very different kind of activity than that of an urban farm. Once a farm starts relating itself to its urban surroundings through products and services (see the “agricultural business models” below), it becomes a whole different story, and many may fall into the ECS businesses that are within our scope. This is particularly true to those farmers who have a systemic and organic approach to their operations and are engaged in, or willing to, redesigning their activities so as to include closed-loop resource management, biodiversity-generating strategies etc.

A simpler distinction may be to look at which farmers receive conventional subsidies by the EU or national agencies - the agricultural funds are not available for non-conventional farmers.

It is our therefore our recommendation that **conventional farms delivering agricultural products to the national or even regional market, fall outside of the scope of EdiCitNet**. In terms of ECS, we consider that those not interdependent of the city’s resources, population and markets (e.g.

industrial scale waste management facilities) also fall outside of the scope of EdiCitNet, however we consider that there may be some good exceptions to the rule.

3.2.3 Is the ECS embedded in the City (Municipality)

When mapping ECS of the Front Runner Cities (Oslo, Rotterdam and Andernach), it is necessary to develop a shared understanding of the geographical limitations that determine which ECS should, and shouldn't, be included in the database. It is particularly useful to consult the City Region Food System (CRFS) Toolkitⁱⁱⁱ that the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) has published on the topic, in collaboration with the RUA Foundation. It provides an overview of current research on CRFS as well as examples of implementation from across the world. A relevant example can be the CRFS of Utrecht in the Netherlands, which according to the FAO can be considered all of these different categories; Utrecht Municipality // U10 Region // Utrecht Province // Stadsgevestig Utrecht // Grootstedelijke agglomerate (Metropolitan Area) // Lekker Utrecht.

Typical CRFS can include **(a)** a strict limitation following the municipal border delimitations; **(b)** Include the main municipality and include the surrounding smaller municipalities that are considered a part of the metropolitan system; **(c)** the city region, which would include rural producers who have direct sales to urban consumers as a main source of income, or **(d)** the watershed region, which would include the geographical area sharing the same physical resources, for example a valley or a river mouth.

For EdiCitNet, we believe that the most appropriate scale for the geographical limitations, would be the strictly municipal interpretation (alternative a) a strict limitation following the municipal border delimitations), mainly since the municipality is a partner of the project. As a political and administrative unit, this is also the structure most able to take the learnings from EdiCitNet and convert them into action during and after the project.

In practice, this means that **ECS should be based on ingredients cultivated/ produced/ taking place within the municipality,** at least mainly. This would exclude some interesting ECSs, such as local sausage producers getting their meat from rural areas, foragers who harvest mushroom in forests in the region – but who prepare their products within the city, and those depending on importing produce for locally made products, for example chilli sauces made from imported chillies, or baked goods from cricket flour originating somewhere else.

3.2.4 Is the product or service on ECS

According to our proposal, ECS *“focus on urban productive landscapes including the wide range of different forms of urban farming, building integrated farming, agro-forestry, aquaculture, biomass production for energy among other productive and ornamental purposes and services combined with closed loop systems for sustainable water, nutrient and waste management”*. The proposal further exemplifies ECS and lists a wide variety of examples ranging from edible green walls and aquaculture to biomass feedstock.

Some activities related to ECS and urban agriculture, do not produce anything edible. A very commonplace example of this, are intra-urban stables/activity centers for horseback riding activities. However, a startup focusing on locally composting, bagging and selling the manure from the stables as high quality fertilizer might be a very good example of an EdiCitNet ECS. Therefore we will need to look carefully at the goods and services produced to see whether we consider them an ECS.

Sometimes, an ECS startup will provide a range of products that are both edible and non-edible. An example of this is Herbanist, an Oslo startup that grow herbs and flowers that they sell to restaurants and bars, and make into products such as teas and herbal spice mixes, - but also non-

edible cosmetics that are sold in markets. As their range of products is mainly edible, and their cultivation provides important ecosystem services at providing pollinator friendly spaces in the city we believe they should be included.

Some products and services indirectly promote ECS by providing the means to such initiatives. We have asked ourselves whether a carpenter, using locally sourced or upcycled materials to build planters, can consider himself an ECS. What if the carpenter employs local vulnerable populations to do some of the jobs? What if it's not a carpenter but a basket weaver growing (or foraging) his/her materials inside the city? This is a grey zone, and there will of course be many of them. If we agree to including these cases, we might need to consider a wider range of suppliers to ECS business and might lose the focus on the overarching objectives of EdiCitNet. For the purpose of WP6 we therefore suggest that we take a rather strict interpretation of ECS, only considering those that directly provide an ECS. However we think this must be judged on a case by case basis and are open for "exceptions to the rule".

Some similar questions may also arise regarding including startups that focus on composting. It integrates well with ECS as a method for developing NBS. The composting itself, whether it is using conventional cold composting, vermicompost or bokashi methods, is an innovative field which is developing important circular solutions for managing city waste, and closing the loop for stakeholders that produce food waste, for example schools or restaurants. The end product, the compost, is also a highly needed ingredient for ECSs to develop services that do not depend on external or non-organic additives. A great example of such a startup, is LeCompostier in Amsterdam, who builds and maintains large worm hotels for schools and neighborhoods, in addition to producing and selling batches of worm compost. **We therefore suggest that circular waste management activities are included in, and strongly encouraged, in the ECS business models that we will work with.**

Similarly, ECS need water and businesses around water, which at the same time provide blue/green water services to the city. They also need nutrients, which may in some way come from sanitation or recycling of organic matter^{iv}.

Other startups have identified other waste sources that they use to promote urban gardening. An example of this is how the NGO Hagecrew organizes workshops where they teach participants to build a planter box from recycled and reclaimed materials. Some might consider this to be an ECS, others might not agree.

3.3 Urban Agriculture Europe Business Models

As mentioned before, most research on ECS has focused on urban agriculture, and had the "looking glasses" of that sector. The research done on business models in UA, has started by defining urban agriculture, and then worked their way through the topic from there onwards. A very solid example of this, is the work done by the research project "COST-action Urban Agriculture Europe" (COST-UAE)^v. This project provides a very useful framework of defining urban farming and urban gardening which has been tested, and resonates, across Europe. It's worth noting that COST-UAE works with definitions of ECS that focus on horticultural production, and many of the innovative ECS that we are currently seeing across Europe, don't fit very well into these categories. This is particularly evident among those ECS businesses whose impact is mainly social and where urban agriculture is a means to make this happen, and ECS businesses that have complex and systemic impacts on urban challenges. **EdiCitNet will need to look at ways to go beyond these categories and update these definitions to include the more innovative urban food initiatives, but we can still learn a lot from the work that has gone into analyzing the sector and the businesses that have come out of it.**

COST-UAE starts by defining two main categories: urban food gardening (UFG) and urban farming (UF), each with a set of well-defined subcategories (Figure 1). UFG includes a range of agricultural activities that focus more on the social goals rather than on the material output (food produced). On the other hand, UF refers more specifically to intentional business models that take advantage of the urban location and the proximity to city-specific market segments.

A third category, which is outside the scope of EdiCitNet, are the conventional farms within the perimeters of the municipality but who orient themselves to the traditional national and international distribution channels and markets. Interestingly, these traditional farmers in the urban regions, often located at the perimeters of the city or even surrounded by the city after urban expansion, can often see ECS initiatives as something negative.

3.3.1 Category A) URBAN FOOD GARDENING (UFG)

Urban food gardening can be divided into two main subcategories: individual production and collective production, based on the ownership (or perceived ownership) of the food produced. The **individual production subcategory** includes family and allotment gardens in urban settings, that provide the owners or tenants with crops such as vegetables and fruits produced on their own land, or even on people’s own balconies or rooftops. Throughout Western Europe, many gardens have become ornamental over the last few decades. In Eastern, and to some extent Southern Europe, it is still quite common to have food-producing gardens to supply families with produce throughout the season. However, with movements such as “Incredible Edible”, “Transition Towns” and similar, many gardens are again becoming productive spaces supporting local resilience and food sovereignty (*reference*). Throughout Europe, rapid urbanization has put both private gardens and allotment gardens under pressure. However, the trend seems to be changing in many places, as the interest in ECS is growing - so is the number of allotments in an increasing number of cities.

Urban food gardens that are in some type of collective or public ownership (**collective production subcategory**) are also an important segment; however, only partly relevant for EdiCitNet and WP6 (consultancy, business development and market uptake). This includes **educational gardens** located on school premises or elsewhere, where student visit regularly to explore gardening and food production through the seasons. **Therapeutical gardens** can be part of for example a mental health care institution or a public botanical garden. Often contemplative (such as sensory gardens for persons suffering from Alzheimer’s), rather than productive, there are more and more institutions looking to food productions as a therapeutical activity for their users, and gradually

more research is also coming out of academic institutions regarding the benefits to public health of such activities (reference).

Community gardens are maybe the most known movement in urban food gardening. It is often the local community gardens that come to mind when people discuss urban farming. They often emerge from local initiatives, and serve a dual purpose of a hub of social activity and a green recreational spot – where food is also grown. As bottom-up initiatives, they are also an important voice for urban populations wanting to reclaim the commons and find concrete and meaningful ways to engage in urban sustainability and social issues. Sometimes, the municipality or other public institutions can also facilitate or establish the creation of community gardens. In other words – community gardens take many organizational, legal and physical shapes, but the one thing that they have in common is the absence of a business model that guides the management of the initiative.

3.3.2 Category B) Urban Farming (UF)

In urban farming, the starting point for these definitions, are former farms now part of an urban agglomeration. Some provide **on-site experiences/services** such as therapeutic, educational or leisure activities, where the focus is on social activities. The second subcategory focuses more on the environmental output (**flows**), where services include food production or providing benefits to the environment such as green biodiversity habitats, flood management or seed production. **As we will see, many of these urban farms have little connection to ECS and therefore fall outside the scope of WP6.**

Leisure and educational farms are mainly located in peri-urban areas and offer a wide range of recreational activities. However, there must be a link to agricultural production (not for example a farmhouse converted to an art gallery. An important stakeholder in many cities, are the farms that host educational programs. They are often geared towards kindergartens and primary schools and offer a place to welcome children and provide them a taste of what farmlife is like, as well as an arena to explore alternative learning strategies.

Many farms, located near or far away from the city, have been establishing alternative funding income sources through providing social services to at-risk communities, they are **social farms**. This strategy has also been adopted by many farms located intra-urban or peri-urban. Services include programs for substance abuse rehabilitation, programs for high-school dropouts or job training for immigrants. These services are often a formalized alternative to municipal services, and framed as either NGO activities or Social Enterprises. They are mainly funded through subsidies, although self-funded business models also exist.

Some farms located in cities, have a specific role as transmitters of national or local agricultural history, are considered **cultural heritage farms**. This can include services to maintain a certain type of landscape, or maintaining buildings of a specific architectural style or historical significance.

Most cities have some sort of collaboration with nearby universities and provide some spaces that are maintained for **experimentation farming** in collaboration with students and faculties. Some municipalities also have land or properties that they use for experiments in collaboration with the agricultural sector, or they outsource the experiments to other properties through providing funding for specific pilots. An example of this, is how the Municipality of Oslo established a collaboration with Nabolagshager to initiate a pilot project on urban rooftop farming with the project “Tak for Maten” to test out a variety of rooftop farming strategies.

Out of all the categories of farms that a city can host, the most relevant to EdiCitNet are maybe the local food + farms. It includes farms that grow goods for the urban consumer market, and often they also produce and sell derivate products from the crops. They benefit from the short distance between the production facilities and those of the customer or consumer, and the

production is highly responsive to emerging needs in the market. This production links the consumer directly to the produces, since there usually are no middle men.

Community-supported agriculture (CSA) has emerged as a very successful business model that builds strong community groups, provides an economic safety net for the farmer through the risk-sharing of the season's produce, as well as very meaningful arenas of dialogue and interactions between experts and novices, facilitators and participants.

3.4 Wageningen University Business Models in Urban Agriculture

In 2015, Wageningen University published a handy overview of business models in urban agriculture^{vi}. Unlike the business models covered in the COST-UAE project, these models are meant for urban agriculture but also apply to a wider set of ECS, and therefore can be more useful to EdiCitNet. Interestingly, the publication specifically mentions that *“the classic management literature is not yet able to interpret these innovative forms of entrepreneurship, let alone advise them on how they can do better”*.

The publication also highlights that success in urban farming often lies in combining these models, and finding combinations that provide synergies. And as opposed to the advice from conventional management literature, the publication highlights the usefulness of not sticking to one specific strategy.

The different models identified are the following;

3.4.1 Differentiation

This strategy focuses on creating distinctions with the conventional supply chains. This can mean growing other specialties than those available in traditional distribution channels, such as heirloom vegetables or microgreens. It also allows the customers to connect with the seasonality of the city's crops through offering harvest festivals or workshops where excess production is processed. Within the differentiation strategy, it is also quite common to do some of the processing and distribution (vertical integration) to increase profits. Many also have innovative business models where the input of volunteers or family members are an important element of keeping costs down.

3.4.2 Diversification

The key to this strategy, is to providing other goods and services, aside from food production, and getting paid for this. The focus is on using the resources you have, in as many ways as possible, and earn an income from this. This is known as “economies of scope”. These are activities that per design go hand in hand with the food production and can include such varied services as child care services, recreation, or landscape maintenance. Many interesting business models that focus on business-to-business activities are also found here, including energy production from urban green waste, recycling and composting, but also corporate events, trainings etc. The main challenge to this business model, is that it can often be challenging to have the urban stakeholders acknowledge the value of these services, and be willing to pay for providing these services. When funding from the public sector is made available, it is often provided on an ad-hoc basis, as opposed to a systematic approach. Even when municipal tenders are published, for services such as social work or park management, ECS businesses may not qualify to participate, meaning that the services are kept in the hands of the established parties.

3.4.3 Low cost

In conventional agriculture and horticulture, specialization and cost reductions are the key means to survival – realizing “economies of scale”. In an urban context, this strategy is often not an option, due to pressure on available spaces. One way to overcome this for urban startups, is to think creatively about spaces, and employ underutilized or unused spaces, both temporarily and permanently. This includes vacant land and empty buildings, and unused urban resources such as compost, rainwater and heat from buildings.

These solutions can be both high-tech and low-tech. Microgreens use technology to maximize the output from a limited area. Permaculture on the other hand, uses no external input to produce an abundance of food.

In order to keep costs low, it is also fairly common to rent spaces and share resources/equipment where possible rather than owning – which also means that the investment and overhead costs are kept reasonably low.

Interestingly, rather than going for the national quality assurance labels such as eco certification, which often has a high initial cost, the quality assurance to the consumer is provided through the direct interactions and transparency of operations.

3.4.4 Reclaiming the commons

One of the most important motivations behind urban agriculture, is the opportunity to engage physically with their surroundings, to regain control of their food supply and learn more about where the food on their plate comes from. The ownership can be directly (through growing your own vegetables on your own property), or indirectly (having contributed to a startup through crowdfunding). Physically participating in the food production by volunteering at ECS, or as members of a community-supported farm, have become popular ways of engaging. These businesses also foment creating new forms of solidarity and shared sense of ownership, responsibility and care.

This business category also shares an important aspect with the “low cost” category, in that it is very common to share resources such as tools, or engaging in bartering with goods. Both are interesting tools for creating more just and sustainable economies.

The use of open source tools is also quite common here, both in terms of infrastructure such as ICT but also directly applied through sharing DIY knowledge on anything from composting to waste water solutions.

3.4.5 Experience

The experience economy is key to this business model. Here, revenue is generated through using the ECS to provide unique and memorable experiences, rather than through the sales of basic goods or services. The urban audience are allowed an experience unlike anything else the city can provide. A rooftop farm, for example, will find it much more economically rewarding to sell the experience of a meal based on the rooftop ingredients, rather than selling the vegetables themselves at a low commodity price per kilo. These are experiences that urbanites are willing to pay a high price for, as they are exclusive, limited edition, and “Instagram-worthy”.

Storytelling and the use of social media is key to this strategy, and facilities are often specifically designed to accommodate this, through “styling” of the environments that provide for good “Instagram spots”, or advocating the use of certain hashtags in their event invitations for example.

One of the most intriguing insights of this strategy, is that it tells a new story of green, urban, lifestyles. It shows the appeal of the rural and urban dynamics and how well they interact if we plan for it. Keeping your own backyard chickens or learning to grow your own tomatoes on your balcony is a personal journey in sustainability, as well as a way to learn first-hand about nature, seasons, and where food comes from.

3.5 Social Innovation in ECS Business

Social enterprises have become a force to reckon with within the European Union.

Oftentimes, it is not the edible city solutions in themselves that are the primary goals of the activities that they englobe, they can rather be the vehicles for other goals, especially objectives related to resolving social challenges that cities are struggling with. An urban garden can be utilized as a job training program for youth that have dropped out from higher education, for refugees in their vulnerable stage of settling down in a new home country, or as an activity program for developmentally challenged persons.

Many of these activities are organized as volunteer programs or NGO-run activities, and as such would not be considered business-oriented activities that would fall within the delimitations of WP6. However, many startups within social enterprises are starting to look to ECS as they build innovative business models that focus as much on environmental impact as on creating positive social change. Inspiring examples of such social enterprises exist across Europe.

ECS coexisting with social innovation can cover a wide range of economic/business concepts. When developing their business ideas, products or services, the company or entrepreneurs will be starting with the social needs identified, and as they look for sources of income independent of public funding sources, grants and similar, some may develop ECS business ideas.

Typical social innovation categories ^{vii}	ECS examples	Case study
Social and economic integration of the disadvantaged and excluded (such as work integration and sheltered employment)	Establishing urban food garden to create employment.	On the outskirts of Bristol (UK), the Severn Project ^{viii} runs a successful business, where high quality salad greens are grown for the local market. The business employs people from socially excluded demographics, including those recovering from drug and alcohol misuse, people with poor mental health, and ex-offenders.
Social services of general interest (such as long term care for the elderly and for people with disabilities; education and child care; employment and training services; social housing; health care and medical services.)	Resolving social challenges through establishing green businesses such as sensory gardens for patients in private care facilities.	Via Gandusio ^{ix} is a social housing complex in Bologna (IT) that host two different communities: advanced-age Italians (former migrants from the south) and current international immigrants from Africa and Asia. The difference of age and nationality create some conflicts and limits the relationships among the community. The community garden was designed with the aim of setting a meeting point for the community

		where food production is the link between neighbours to exchange knowledge, culture and experiences.
Other public services such as community transport, maintenance of public spaces, etc.	As public services they are not directly paid by the user/consumer, but the gardening/maintenance of such spaces can be done by a social enterprise.	After the financial crisis, and the end of the construction bubble, many urban voids in Spain were transformed, with or without the permissions of the municipality and/or owners into innovative public spaces centered around urban gardening and recycling. However few of them are based around business models.
Strengthening democracy, civil rights and digital participation;	One may argue that “knowledge is power”, and social enterprises working on topics such as environmental justice and empowerment may fall in this category. Many times, however, these impacts are more indirect results rather than main objectives.	Demokratiödling ^x is a program developed by the social enterprise BOODLA in Stockholm (SE), that provides leadership training for at-risk youth, through engaging them in urban gardening, as a means to cultivate empowerment and participation in society. The courses are free to attend, and the main customers of the social enterprise, are various municipalities that buy these services.
Environmental activities such as reducing emissions and waste (recycling), renewable energy;	There are many business models surrounding environmental + social services. These can include services such as beekeeping, composting and wastewater management.	In the Czech Republic, a well-known example of social innovation in ECS, is the small business KOKOZA ^{xi} . The company employs mainly socially disadvantaged people as well as mentally disabled people, and they are engaged in creating community gardens and building composters. In their workshop they also produce mobile gardens and seed bombs, among other products. By combining these products and services with their social innovation, the company is resolving multiple local challenges at once.
Practising solidarity with developing countries (such as promoting fair trade).	As we define Edicitet ECS as limited to the products coming from within the municipality, fair trade programs would not qualify. However, a related aspect of this would be ECS cooperatives where food producers and	Cooperative supermarkets that charge membership fees and ask members to work on staff for three hours’ a month in return for cheaper goods are rising in popularity across France. Members of these stores are clients, owners, and employees all at once. La Louve ^{xii} in Paris (FR) is one of many of these supermarkets that have become very popular over the

	consumers join forces to ensure that the price paid is worth the work put into the product. Many of these models are membership based.	last few years. La Louve promotes itself as a food cooperative with the goal to make good things accessible to everyone through a type of shop that's reliable, lively and socially supportive, and that operates on a non-profit basis.
Combined models	Across the cases we have studied, we find many examples of social enterprises that combine more than one social/environmental goal, and to many entrepreneurs as well as for their customers, this is one of the strengths – the ability to combine varied goals.	In Copenhagen (DK), the urban beekeepers of ByBi have developed a very successful range of product, including honey-based candies, honey-based IPA beer and rum, as well as a very popular range of corporate gift baskets. Their main beekeeper is a refugee from Syria and the company also collaborates with many other social initiatives within the city, all while making a solid profit, demonstrating that creating and maintaining urban biodiversity and providing pollination, while achieving social goals, can indeed make business sense.

3.6 Innovative Funding Mechanisms and Financial Aspects of ECS Businesses

In the field of circular innovation, green entrepreneurship and social innovation, many innovative economic strategies are being tested. They range from exploring bartering and local currencies, to harvesting the benefits of social media through crowdfunding campaigns. Many great examples of this exist in urban agriculture and exploring these further will provide inspiration for future ECS initiatives. However, in our introductory mapping of ECS businesses, we have found few sources that go in depth on these aspects.

Oftentimes, funding mechanism and financial instruments reflect cultural aspects such as trust and degree of risk aversion. It is therefore worth recognizing that some of these innovative strategies may not be equally easy to translate and implement across Europe, but they will still provide relevant inspiration.

Crowdsourcing is one example of an innovative funding mechanism. Crowdsourcing for ECS gained much of its fame from the American fundraising portals Kickstarter and Indiegogo, that have been great sources for start capital for many American ECS startups. Gradually, European counterparts are looking more often to these strategies too. A great example of the application of crowdsourcing, is the Oslo ECS startup GRUTEN. This company specializes in upcycling used coffee grounds for mushroom production. Additionally, they host a range of courses and make and sell skin care products made from coffee grounds. When Gruten first established a shop and course facility location, they launched a crowdsourcing campaign, where consumers could get rewards such as handmade soaps made from their coffee grounds as one of the smallest rewards, to getting

their name on a plank on the wall of the social space of the premises. Now, a few years later, Gruten has conducted another effective crowdsourcing campaign^{xiii}, this time to fund the refurbishing of two shipping containers into an oyster cultivation facility. With the support of more than 200 fans, past and future customers, Gruten managed to raise more than NOK 90,000 (Appx EUR 9,500) in the scope of only a couple of days. In addition to providing the funds needed for infrastructure, Gruten has also been very successful in building long-term relationships with a wide customer base through these fundraising activities.

Community-supported business models and cooperatives have also become an increasingly popular framework for startups to connect with either consumers or producers. Community-supported agriculture, CSAs, have become a very popular way of becoming a “member” and “co-producer” under the management and mentorship of

To promote circular innovation, it has also become increasingly popular to sell “goods as services”, in other words to establish innovative subscription services, where the business provides a running service, and thereby also the continuous maintenance and correct disposal of, or upcycling of, waste that results from the usage.

Funding for innovative services and solutions may be difficult at the start. Thus, cities or countries may want to set up specific funding facilities tailored to the needs of ECS or more widely to green economy solutions and their promotion. See for example the \$100 million grant investment fund bankrolled by the government of New Zealand.

4. Conclusions

As an emerging field, ECS businesses are far from a mature market or segment. We are certain that the speed of innovation will only increase in the coming years, and that new business models, solutions and funding mechanisms will arise across the continent. We hope that EdiCitNet will provide fertile ground for enhancing this process.

As we conclude the very initial stages of work package 6, we have identified many exciting cases of innovative ECSs across the continent and in our front runner cities Oslo, Rotterdam and Andernach, as well as in other EU countries (see appendix). It has also become very evident that there are large gaps in current research and practice regarding ECS businesses. It is our hope and expectation that we over the next few years will be able to close as many of those gaps as possible.

We consider some of the main “missing pieces” currently to be the following;

- Business models that successfully facilitate systemic ECS initiatives
- Business models that look beyond UA to englobe the full scope of ECS needed in order to make a meaningful impact
- Integrating experiences, success stories and business models from social enterprises and social innovation with ECS
- Explore circular ECS business models that benefit from “goods as services”
- Explore funding mechanisms that can facilitate a rapid growth of ECS businesses

5. Interactive Register of ECS

This interactive register is constantly growing. This table is provided by Nabolagshager and updated throughout the project time. These data will be pushed as available data into the Toolbox (WP7).

See below a screenshot.

ECS COMPANY	LOCATION	ORGANIZATION FORM	KEY PRODUCT/ SERVICE	SHORT DESCRIPTION	PRIMARY URBAN AG BUSINESS MODEL	SECONDARY URBAN AG BUSINESS MODEL	3BMC VALUE PROPOSITION (ECONOMIC)	3BMC FUNCTIONAL VALUE (ENVIRONMENTAL)	3BMC SOCIAL VALUE (SOCIAL)	SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS MODEL ARCHETYPE	B2B	B2C	WEBSITE/ E-MAIL	SOCIAL MEDIA	ESTABLISHED YEAR	OTHER COMMENTS
No Chateau	NL - Amsterdam		City vineyard	Participants manage their own allotment of vineyard and harvest their products. Social inclusion and educational purposes.									http://www.nochateau.nl/			
De Ceuveil	NL - Amsterdam		Aquaponic Greenhouse	Old and polluted industrial area transformed into a sustainable residential area by creating circularity for waste materials and nutrients. The aquaponic greenhouse is just one piece of the chain and contributes to close the nutrient cycle. Vegetable and herbs are destined for Café de Ceuveil.									http://deceuveil.nl/nl/a-bout/sustainable-technology/#			
GROWx	NL - Amsterdam		Plant factory (with artificial lighting)	High tech vertical farm producing more than 20 types of fresh vegetables, with the use of LED lights, renewable energy and circular packaging.									https://growx.co/			
QO amsterdam	NL - Amsterdam		Rooftop greenhouse	The philosophy of QO hotel is to create a physical, mental and emotional experience for the hosts. It tries to meet sustainability and circularity thanks to energy saving construction options, innovative moving facade to control the indoor climate and a rooftop greenhouse with 70 kinds of herbs, vegetables and fish.									https://www.qo-amsterdam.com/restaurant-and-bar/			
Restaurant de kas	NL - Amsterdam		Greenhouse	Production of vegetables and herbs. Restaurant inside the greenhouse itself.									https://www.restaurantdekas.nl/over-de-kas			
De Haagse Stadswijngaard	NL - Den Haag		City vineyard	Wine production within the city. Citizen participation, social events and making wine courses/demonstrations.									http://haagsestadswijngaard.nl/			
Urban Farmers De Schiloe (bankrupt)	NL - Den Haag		Rooftop greenhouses/aquaponic	1200 m ² of greenhouse and a 900 m ² of space for fish cultivation on the roof and 6th floor of De Schiloe building, respectively. They declared bankruptcy at the end of June 2018. It is unclear a possible restart.									https://urbanfarmers.nl/?SD=70878172&sdmfc=2d0r3a1d			
Noortzee Boerderij	NL - Den Haag		Seaweed farm	The idea is to encourage seaweed production sectors in the Netherlands. They provide test farms available to pilot, scaling up and research into multifunctional concepts (e.g. cultivation of seaweed, shellfish and other flora and fauna; ecology and biodiversity).									https://www.noortzeeboerderij.nl/			
Haagsezwam	NL - Den Haag		Mushrooms on ground coffee wastes	Cultivation of oyster mushrooms on coffee grounds and other residual products. Delivery by bike in a range of 10 km.									https://haagsezwam.nl/			
Het Zoete Land	NL - Leiden		open field	Production of vegetables, herbs, flowers and fruit. Social inclusion as harvest participant or volunteer and educational purposes.									https://www.hetzoeteland.nl/			
Open veld leven	BE - Leuven		Mixed organic farming	Animals, vegetables and processed products. School garden meant for children. Teacher residents show how the									http://www.boerencompagnie.be/			
				School garden meant for children. Teacher residents show how the									https://esthaam.nl/mensen			

Figure 1: Interactive table of ECS

6. Literature

ⁱ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/business>

ⁱⁱ Urban Agriculture Europe, Lohrberg, Frank et al, Jovis Verlag, Berlin, 2016,

ⁱⁱⁱ <http://www.fao.org/3/i9255en/I9255EN.pdf>

^{iv} Xin Ma et al. Sustainable Water Systems for the City of Tomorrow – A Conceptual Framework, Sustainability 2015; doi: 10.3390/su70912071

^v Ibid

^{vi} https://www.wur.nl/upload_mm/f/3/6/fb858e59-2190-46d9-8fe7-f293efd8c0a8_MFL_Business%20models%20urban%20agriculture.%20Juni%202015%20Small.pdf

^{vii} “A map of social enterprises and their eco-systems in Europe”, European Commission (2015)

<https://ec.europa.eu/social/BlobServlet?docId=12988&langId=en>

^{viii} <http://www.thesevernproject.org/>

^{ix} <https://susturbanfoods.com/2016/07/13/case-study-community-garden-of-via-gandusio-bologna-italy/>

^x <https://boodla.se/demokratiodling/>

^{xi} <https://www.facebook.com/KOKOZAops/>

^{xii} <https://www.facebook.com/CoopLaLouve/>

^{xiii} <https://www.culturaflokk.no/prosjekt/grutensopp-til-folket/-fa455932-cfc2-4748-b01d-d4cedf32e113>

Thank you!

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